

Another BRICS in the wall? The BRICS' countries stance towards the 2026 US and Israel attacks on Iran

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Abstract

The 2026 military strikes conducted by the United States and Israel against Iran reignited debates concerning the limits of the prohibition of the use of force under the United Nations Charter. This article analyses the official reactions of BRICS states to the attacks in order to assess whether the bloc is emerging as a coherent interpretive community in the evolution of the *jus ad bellum* regime. By examining diplomatic statements from Brazil, Russia, China, India and South Africa, the article evaluates how these states framed the legality of the attacks, particularly regarding anticipatory self-defence and proportionality. The findings suggest that although several BRICS members articulated legal arguments rejecting the use of force without Security Council authorization, the absence of a unified position reveals the bloc's limited capacity to function as a collective interpretive actor in shaping the contemporary debates.

Keywords: Use of force; BRICS; Self-defence; UN Charter.

Introduction

On 28 February 2026, the United States and Israel conducted coordinated military strikes against targets in the Islamic Republic of Iran. According to reports discussed within the United Nations system, the attacks resulted in significant casualties and occurred only days after a new round of indirect negotiations between the United States and Iran aimed at extending the framework governing Iran's nuclear programme and its commitments under the international non-proliferation regime (United Nations News, 2026). The proximity between diplomatic negotiations and the resort to force immediately raised concerns regarding the implications of the operation for the stability of the international legal order.

These events reopen a debate concerning the existing tensions in the regime of the prohibition of the use of force under the Charter of the United Nations. Article 2(4) of that document establishes one of the foundational norms of the contemporary international legal system by requiring that "all Members shall refrain in their international relations from the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any state" (United Nations, 1945). This rule has widely been interpreted as reflecting not only treaty law but also customary international law, and is often regarded as possessing a *jus cogens* character (Gray, 2018, p. 32).

The Charter recognizes only limited exceptions to this prohibition. Article 51, for example, preserves the inherent right of self-defence in the event of an armed attack, while Chapter VII empowers the United Nations Security Council to determine the existence of a "threat to the peace", "breach of the peace", or "act of aggression" and to adopt measures necessary to maintain or restore international peace and security. The interpretation of these provisions has nonetheless remained contested in both state practice and legal scholarship (Akande; Johnston, 2021).

A central controversy raised by the 2026 strikes concerns the recurring invocation of anticipatory or preventive self-defence. In classical international law discourse, this notion has often been associated with the so-called Caroline doctrine, which established that self-defence may be justified only when the necessity is instant, overwhelming and leaves no other choice of means and no moment for deliberation (Brownlie, 1963, p. 275). The adoption of the United Nations Charter substantially narrowed the scope for unilateral uses of force by conditioning the exercise of self-defence upon the occurrence of an armed attack, however, the legal reasoning advanced by the U.S. following the February 2026 strikes still appears to fall outside this category and reflect a preventive logic.

In the official statement announcing the operation, U.S. authorities justified the attack as necessary "(...) to prevent this radical dictatorship from threatening American national security interests" (PBS Newshour, 2026). Such reasoning conflicts with the restrictive interpretation of Article 51 commonly defended in contemporary international law.

The Iranian response further complicates the legal assessment of the crisis. Although Iran invoked self-defence following the attacks on its territory, retaliatory strikes directed against several Gulf states raised additional questions concerning proportionality and the permissible scope of defensive action under Article 51.

The episode acquired additional political significance due to Iran's recent accession to the expanded BRICS+ grouping. Between 2024 and 2025, the BRICS coalition underwent a significant enlargement process that incorporated several new members, including Iran. Although BRICS was originally conceived as an economic coordination forum, its increasing geopolitical relevance has led scholars to consider whether the bloc may gradually contribute to shaping diplomatic narratives and legal interpretations within international institutions. The attacks against Iran therefore provide a case through which to analyse the legal and diplomatic positioning of BRICS states. If the bloc were evolving toward a more cohesive geopolitical actor, one might expect some degree of convergence in the legal arguments advanced by its members in response to a direct attack against one of its states.

This article examines the official reactions of BRICS member states to the February 2026 attacks in order to identify possible patterns of convergence or divergence in their legal narratives regarding the use of force. By analysing how BRICS states articulated their legal positions in response to the crisis, the article seeks to contribute to a broader discussion concerning the role of emerging powers in shaping contemporary interpretations of the *jus ad bellum* regime.

Positions of the BRICS States regarding the 2026 Attacks on Iran

Interpretive Significance of State Positions within BRICS

The reactions of individual BRICS member states provide a useful perspective through which to examine the dynamics surrounding the prohibition of the use of force in contemporary international law. Even in the absence of a coordinated collective declaration of the bloc, statements issued by the separate states constitute relevant elements of state practice and may also contribute to the clarification of legal norms and their interpretation (International Law Commission, 2018).

Within the framework of customary international law, the development of legal rules depends upon the convergence of state practice accompanied by *opinio juris* (Shaw, 2017, p. 54). Official governmental statements, diplomatic protests and formal legal justifications therefore represent important sources through which states articulate their understanding of the applicable (or not) legal framework governing the use of force.

In that direction, the United Nations Security Council represents one of the most important

institutional settings in which such interpretive processes occur. Although Article 39 of the UN Charter empowers the Council to determine the existence of a “threat to the peace”, “breach of the peace”, or “act of aggression”, the Charter itself provides no precise definitions for these categories. Their operational meaning has therefore been developed through institutional practice and the legal arguments advanced by states, especially when participating in Security Council deliberations (De Wet, 2004, p. 133).

In this sense, the interpretation of the Charter’s collective security provisions is shaped not only by formal decisions of the Council but also by the justificatory discourse surrounding those decisions. Legal argumentation within the Security Council constitutes a form of deliberative practice in which participants seek to justify their positions in terms that are acceptable within the broader international legal community (Johnstone, 2003). Through this process, states gradually contribute to defining the boundaries of permissible interpretations of the Charter’s provisions on the use of force.

The debate surrounding anticipatory self-defence dialogues with the importance of this interpretive dynamic. While some states have attempted to justify preventive military action, many argue that the adoption of the UN Charter significantly narrowed the permissible scope of unilateral uses of force by conditioning self-defence upon the occurrence of an armed attack (Gray, 2018, p. 1-31). Thus, attempts to legitimize preventive uses of force often generate competing legal narratives within the international community – statements rejecting anticipatory self-defence or emphasizing the requirements of proportionality and necessity implicitly reaffirm a restrictive interpretation of Article 51. Conversely, diplomatic silence or more cautious formulations may signal reluctance to engage directly with this legal debate.

Within this interpretive environment, the positions of BRICS states acquire particular relevance. The group includes two permanent members of the Security Council (namely Russia and China) as well as influential emerging powers. Although BRICS itself does not constitute a security institution, the legal language employed by its members contributes to shaping the broader diplomatic discourse through which the legality of the use of force is debated within the United Nations system.

The following sections analyse the official reactions adopted by Brazil, Russia, China, India and South Africa following the attacks of 28 February 2026 in order to identify patterns of convergence and divergence in their legal narratives regarding the use of force.

Brazil

Brazil adopted a position explicitly condemning the US-Israeli attacks while at the same time emphasizing the need for diplomatic de-escalation of the conflict as a whole in the region. In its official press statement issued on 28 February 2026, the Brazilian government expressed “grave concern” regarding the strikes conducted by the United States and Israel and

highlighted that the attacks occurred amid ongoing diplomatic negotiations concerning Iran's nuclear programme (Brasil, 2026a), for what Iran and the US had met a week earlier.

Moreover, Brazil also articulated a clear position regarding the scope and use of self-defence. In a subsequent statement addressing the escalation of hostilities in the Gulf region, the government emphasized that self-defence under Article 51 constitutes an exceptional legal mechanism, stating that: "legitimate defence (...) is an exceptional measure subject to proportionality and a causal link with the armed attack" (Brasil, 2026b).

By emphasizing the requirements of proportionality and causal linkage to an armed attack, the position reflects the restrictive interpretation of Article 51 commonly defended in contemporary international legal doctrine (Gray, 2018, p.1-31). Brazil also condemned Iran's retaliatory attacks affecting third states in the region, highlighting the risks of regional escalation and reaffirming the centrality of diplomatic solutions and respect for state sovereignty.

Thus, the declarations therefore situate the crisis within the classical Charter framework governing the use of force, rejecting expansive interpretations of self-defence while simultaneously criticizing retaliatory actions that risk broadening the conflict.

Russia

Moscow articulated the strongest legal condemnation among the BRICS members. In their statement issued on 28 February 2026, the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs described the operation as: "(...) a deliberate, premeditated and unprovoked act of armed aggression against a sovereign and independent UN member state" (Russia, 2026).

This statement further argued that the strikes violated fundamental principles of international law, including the prohibition of the use of force, the principle of non-intervention and the obligation of peaceful settlement of disputes. Russian officials also warned that attacks against facilities operating under International Atomic Energy Agency safeguards could undermine the global nuclear non-proliferation regime.

By explicitly invoking the concept of armed aggression, Russia framed the incident in terms directly relevant to the Security Council's powers and language under Article 39 of the UN Charter. This situates the attacks within the gravest legal category available in the collective security framework and reflects a clear rejection of the preventive logic underlying the justification advanced by the United States.

China

China, just like Brazil and Russia, also condemned the attacks, framing its position primarily in the defence of sovereignty and territorial integrity – as its Ministry of Foreign Affairs

stated that Iran's "sovereignty, security and territorial integrity should be respected" (China, 2026). China further called for the immediate cessation of military operations and urged all parties to return to dialogue and diplomacy. Although less legalistic than the Russian statement, China's position situates the incident within the normative framework of the UN Charter and reiterates its longstanding diplomatic emphasis on the prohibition of unilateral uses of force without Security Council authorization.

By doing so, privileging the scope of its declaration towards sovereignty and non-interference, China is also implicitly rejecting legal narratives that would justify preventive military action outside the collective security mechanisms in the Charter.

India

The current chair of the BRICS+ adopted a less active position than the other members. Its official statement expressed concern regarding the escalation of tensions in the region and called for restraint, protection of civilians and a return to diplomatic dialogue (India, 2026). However, India refrained from namely condemning the attacks conducted by the United States and Israel.

Instead, the statement emphasized India's national interests in regional stability, through their importance to the energy security and trade flows, reflecting the state's complex geopolitical relationships in the Middle East. The state maintains close defence cooperation with Israel while simultaneously preserving important economic and energy partnerships with other Gulf states.

In that sense, India later condemned Iranian retaliatory strikes against targets in the region – illustrating how each member's geopolitical considerations may shape the legal discourse in situations involving strategic partners. It is worth mentioning that a couple of days prior to the attacks, the Indian Prime Minister visited Netanyahu, showing their shared agendas. By avoiding explicit legal characterization of the initial strikes, India effectively remained outside the core legal debate concerning anticipatory self-defence, and defended their interests outside of the BRICS.

South Africa

Finally, in its official statement, the government of South Africa, like most of the other members, explicitly rejected the legality of anticipatory self-defence, affirming that: "(...) Article 51 of the UN Charter provides for self-defence only when a state has been subjected to an armed invasion. Anticipatory self-defence is not permitted under international law" (South Africa, 2026).

The state also characterized the attacks as clear violations of Article 2(4) of the Charter and called on all parties to act in accordance with international law and international humanitarian

law. At the same time, the country condemned Iranian retaliatory strikes against several Gulf states, arguing that such actions exceeded the limits permitted under Article 51 and violated the sovereignty of the affected states.

This two sided condemnation, so to speak, reflects a consistent legal approach by South Africa, as both preventive military action and disproportionate retaliatory strikes are incompatible with the Charter framework and regime governing the use of force.

Conclusion

The reactions of BRICS member states to the February 2026 strikes against Iran reveal a fragmented legal landscape rather than the emergence of a unified interpretive position within the bloc regarding the regulation of the use of force. Several members (including Brazil, Russia, China and South Africa) framed their responses within the classical framework of the United Nations Charter. Their statements emphasized core principles such as sovereignty, territorial integrity and the prohibition of the use of force under Article 2(4). In particular, Brazil and South Africa articulated explicit legal arguments concerning the restrictive scope of self-defence under Article 51, emphasizing the requirements of necessity and proportionality and went further by explicitly rejecting anticipatory self-defence, affirming that Article 51 applies only in response to an armed attack.

At the same time, other statements also criticized Iranian retaliatory strikes against targets in the Gulf region, suggesting that the legality of defensive responses remains subject to the customary constraints of necessity and proportionality. This highlights an important aspect of the State's positions, that both preventive uses of force and disproportionate retaliatory actions may fall outside the limits established by the Charter system.

In any case, despite these converging elements, the reactions of BRICS states did not translate into a unified position, as India, the current president of the bloc adopted a more cautious posture, refraining from condemning the attacks and instead emphasizing restraint, regional stability and national interests – and finally, condemning Iran's actions. Although this factor lies outside a strictly legal analysis, it may partially explain why the bloc did not issue a joint statement comparable to that adopted during the 2025 crisis.

This divergence outsources the structural limits of BRICS as a collective and cohesive actor in matters of international peace and security. Unlike security organizations, BRICS operates first and foremost as a diplomatic coordination forum in which member states retain autonomy in articulating their foreign policy positions. Consequently, the bloc's capacity to generate coherent legal narratives concerning the use of force remains constrained by the geopolitical diversity (and interests) of its members.

Nevertheless, each individual statement of BRICS members remains legally significant, as noted in the doctrine of customary international law – given that official governmental

statements may constitute relevant elements of state practice and *opinio juris*, contributing to the interpretation and gradual development of legal norms (SHAW, 2017, p. 52-55). Even in the absence of coordinated action, such statements individually form part of the broader interpretive environment through which international law evolves (as it would normally, outside of the group or an organization).

The BRICS currently appears to operate as a plural interpretive space, within which distinct legal narratives coexist. While several members reinforce the restrictive interpretation of the Charter framework, others adopt more cautious or strategically ambiguous positions. The result is not a unified normative bloc but a heterogeneous coalition whose members participate individually in the evolving interpretive debates surrounding the use of force.

Ultimately, the reactions to the 2026 attacks on Iran suggest that BRICS has not yet consolidated itself as a coherent interpretive community in matters of collective security. Rather than forming a new “brick” in the normative architecture of the international legal order, the bloc currently functions as a forum in which multiple legal narratives coexist within the broader interpretive processes shaping contemporary law.

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